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**Comparative Analysis of United Nations'
Roles in Gulf Crisis (1990-1991) and
Ukraine-Russian Conflict (2022-2025)**

Chukwu CHRISTIAN

*Department of Politics and International
Relations, Lead City University, Ibadan Nigeria*
aedueducation@gmail.com, +2348080397804

EmmaJimo EMMAJIMO

*Department of Politics and International
Relations, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria*
emma.jimo@lcu.edu.ng,
saintlvemmajimo@gmail.com, +2347032306834

Abstract

In Gulf Crisis, the Middle East was a region split by multitude of different national interests and personal interests of various ideological and hegemonic ruling classes. On the other hand, the Russian-Ukraine conflict was degenerating into deeper and dangerous dimensions in defence of national interest, and UN is helpless to use resolutions to end the conflict. The objective of this study is to examine the factors that limits UN's application of force to end the conflict in Ukraine as in Gulf Crisis. The UN rejected clumsy reasons of annexation of Kuwait sovereignty, but in 2014 Russia annexed Crimea and subsequently took over four other regions in 2022. The research employed qualitative contents analysis method of secondary data using force theory as its framework. The study noted that historical grievances were remote causes of Russian-Ukrainian Conflict. While the quest for expansion and lack of love on both side of Iraq and America led to the Gulf conflicts. The finding shows that UN is helpless with veto power states. The research concludes that Russian possession of veto has made UN subject of debate in realization of

world peace. The study recommends that UN should mandate US to vacate its buffer Zone out of Ukraine; and should negotiate a win – win relations with Ukraine and Russian to avoid another World War.

Keywords: Annexation, Gulf Crisis, Ukraine-Russia Conflict, United Nations, National Interest, Expansion, Historical Grievances

Introduction

The failure of League of Nations formed in 1919 to maintain global peace led to the formation of United Nations Organization (UNO) after World War II at San Francisco, United States of America in October 24th 1945 (Hiscock, 1977: 38). The functions and powers of the League of Nations were formally transferred to United Nations Organization and the League of Nations voted itself out of existence. The UNO was established as an instrument of global peace to prevent further carnage, destruction of human lives due to wars and to protect independent territorial sovereign states from external threat, military aggression and political annexation of independent nations. The charter was officially signed by 51 member states of the world in attendant. Article 1 (1) of the UN Charter stated that the organization shall maintain international peace and security; and it shall take effective collective measures for the prevention and removal of threat to peace and for the suppression of acts of aggression or breaches of peace; and to bring about peaceful means and in conformity with the principles of justice and international law, adjustment and settlement of international disputes or situations which might lead to a breach of the peace (Kelly,.2002:98). President Harry S. Truman said in the inaugural meeting of UNO in 1945: “We have created a great instrument for peace, security and human progress in the world. The world must now use it and the successful use of this instrument requires united will and determination” (Hiscock, 1977: 40).

In 1991, United Nations was able to maintain its Charter obligations in the Gulf Crisis after Iraqi annexed Kuwaiti territory in 1990 as its nineteenth province. The UN coalition of military alliance forced Iraq to surrender unconditionally and Kuwait regained its territory. Altogether, the philosophy behind the institution – United Nations was achieved in the Gulf crisis, but paradoxically, it could not control annexation Crimea on 27th February, 2014 and other four Ukrainian cities of Donetsk, Zaporizhia, Luhansk and Kherson regions, between August to November, 2022. The UN failed to activate its charter against Russia. The question is what went

wrong with UN in ensuring world peace for mutual inter dependence of Nations in line with its charter? Similarly, the organization was unable to control smaller conflicts throughout the world such as genocides in Czech Republics, Kosovo, Rwanda, Burundi, Somalia, Sudan and recently Israel/Palestine Crisis which has dishonoured all manner of United Nations (Washington Post, 2025).

On Russian invasion of Ukraine, Marco Rubio the US Secretary of State was quoted thus: “We have to make a determination about whether this is an endeavour that we want to continue to be involved in or if it is time to sort of focus on some other issues that are equally if not more important in some cases” (Edward, 2025). To this, the United Nations seems to have lost its muzzle to tackle Russia militarily. There are many questions to answer in relation to the organization performances against Iraq over annexation of Kuwaiti territory in 1990. For example, Article 33 paragraph 1 of the charter stated that – “Parties to any disputes which is likely to endanger the maintenance of international peace and security shall first of all seek a solution through negotiation, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, judicial, settlement, resort to regional agencies or arrangement or other peaceful means of their own choices” (Rumki, 2004:26). The Charter provides power to the permanent members of UN Security Council – Britain, Russia, China, France and United States of America to act militarily against any recalcitrant and transgressing states. Each five permanent members has a power of ‘Veto’, which means ‘No’ vote among the big five means against to any action – matter suspended. The UN as a body has no outstanding army as an international organization, but members usually contribute military forces against a deviant state.

Charles Darwin, in his book, *Origin of Species*, observed that in the future an endless number of the lower races will be eliminated by the higher civilized races throughout the world (Awake Magazine, 1998). He summed it up to the struggle for existence and survival of the fittest. Human Rights declaration, according to Eleanor Roosevelt, former United States of America first lady on 10th December, 1948 described the document as - Long Job Finished (Awake Magazine, 1998). Reason, because in 1947 deep disagreement mired the 18-member commission in an endless dispute, the Chinese delegates felt that the document should include philosophy of Confucius; United States Championed Bill of Rights while Soviets delegates wanted to include the ideas of Karl Marx. Kofi Annan the UN Secretary

General while addressing world leaders on Gulf Crisis said: “Just as there is no need to rewrite the Bible or the Koran, there is no need to adjust the declaration. What needs to be adjusted is not the text of the universal declaration, but the behaviour of its discipline” (Awake Magazine, 1998: 2).

Statement of the Problem

The Iraqi invasion of Kuwait in 1990 and its aftermath was overwhelming, but Russian invasion of Ukraine territories made UN toothless. In Iraq, the unconditional withdrawal expired on January, 15 1991 the Allied Forces led by United States launched air and land attacks, in less than three months the result was disgraceful surrender by Iraq. However, Vladimir Putin annexed Crimea under Ukraine sovereignty in 2014 and UN muzzle was relaxed, thereby setting dangerous precedence to international community. The behaviour of Russia is centrifugal to Article 1 of UN Charter and yet the UN and USA are helpless in arresting the developmental trends in Ukraine. President Trump said after his impromptu meeting with President Volodymyr Zelenskyy at Vatican City inauguration of Pope Leo XIV: “On Russian escalating bombardment of Ukraine, it makes me think that maybe Vladimir Putin doesn’t want to end the war, he’s tapping me along and has to be dealt with differently” (Tim & Robert, 2025). Dealing Putin differently might not be with force because both states possess nuclear power and may wish to avoid global calamity. The Russian president demanded international recognition of Crimea as a state distinct from Ukraine territory (Wall Street Journal 2025). The United States of America, and the United Nations are on peace negotiation not war against Russia. Russia is a member of the Security Council and she has a power of veto to dangle on decisions of the UN General Assembly resolutions. In Gulf Crisis, UN members contributed troops against Iraq and less than three months in 1991 Iraq surrendered. Regrettably none have contributed troop against Russia annexation of Ukraine. The context of this research is that United Nations’ response to the Gulf Crisis was marked by fiat and decisive action, including immediate authorization of military deployment to liberate Kuwait. On the contrary, the UN’s response to the Ukraine–Russia conflicts have been sluggish and limited making the UN subject of debate on its effectiveness to maintain world peace.

Objective of the Research

1. To examine the UN responses to the Gulf Crisis (1990-1991) conflict in relation to what has been the UN's response to Ukraine–Russia (2022 - 2025) conflicts, outcome and challenges.
2. To search for differences and similarities between the UN's roles in these two conflicts, and implications of these differences to the effectiveness of the UN as a global peace institution.

Research Questions

1. How did the UN respond to the Gulf Crisis, and Ukraine-Russia conflict outcomes/challenges?
2. What are the key differences and similarities between UN's roles in the two conflicts and implications in combating future conflicts?

Literature Review

The Iraqi Kuwaiti Crisis marked a turning point on UN. It was an interesting episode in global history of international community, coincidentally the Ukraine – Russia conflicts has been subject of debate on UN effectiveness. The literature seeks to analyze concepts, comments, and experts' views emanating from UN roles in both conflicts.

Conflict

Conflict exists when people pursue different interests, opinion, ideology, and values. It exists when the goals of different participants are inherently incompatible; a behaviour which occurs when two or more parties are in opposition or in a battle as a result of perceived relative deprivation. The Marxist scholars see conflict from economic domination and deprivation by one social group against another. The Marxist agree that the desire to control resources has influence on the type of political, economic and socio structure put in place in every society. Such structure is characterized by domination of governing or the ruling class which often makes conflict inevitable. In general, conflict can be defined as a disagreement between two or more parties or groups who perceived threat to their needs, interests, aspirations and wants. Key words in the above definitions are disagreement, parties are involved, and there are threats, interests, needs, aspirations, ideology and wants as the propelling forces in conflict situation (Obizulike-Osufia 2013).

Obizulike-Osufia (2013) identified conflict in three levels:

1. **Blips:** Conflict at blips level is a situation when an incidence happened at first time and much are not at stake. Under this level of analysis, anger is mild but there may be no continued pattern of relationship.
2. **Clashes:** In clashes conflict, contradictions are not happening for the first time. The parties to clashes are aggrieved because of repetitive negative behaviour of one of the parties to the dispute. This level of conflict may lead to tension, anger, and retaliatory measures as in the case of Ukraine - Russian conflict.
3. **Crisis:** In this level, the issue has escalated and become violent. At domestic level, the national government has to suppress the uprising using the instrument of coercion at their disposal depending on the magnitude of the crisis. Vulnerable persons such as women, children, elderly and physically challenged groups are emotionally endangered by this level of conflict.

Collective Security

The issue of collective security has been a paramount concern to the UN since its inception. Evan Luards, (1996) sees collective security as depending on willingness of all states to rally round to defend any other state that is attacked. Luards, (1996) posit that to make the system work, government must take no account of loyalties, national or ideological nor relate the costs to be borne by taking part in an action or national benefits to be gained.

Analysis and Critique

The issue of collective security in line with Article 1 of UN Charter implementation is often problematic because the charter emphasis on maintenance of international peace and security; yet the organization endorses use of force against Iraq to effect removal of threat to peace and aggression in Kuwait. Luards, (1996) idea that states should not count the cost of participating in international peace as suggested was not conceivable because national interest is a driving force in international relations. For instance, USA led Allied Forces during the Gulf Conflicts as a contribution for restoration of peace in the Gulf region. If American gesture was not for interest, why not sponsor budgets for UN against Russia invasion of Ukraine sovereignty. In compliance of the rules of Article 1, some peace proposals of Iraq friends were rejected by United States and Great Britain

based on interest. Even three points Peace proposals by Iran, the Iraqi former foe were based on interest:

- a. First, regional resolution of the conflict among the Arab nations,
- b. Settlement of Palestine crisis, and
- c. Dropping of economic sanctions once majority of Iraqi forces left Kuwait (Iwobi, 1991: 4).

These were all rejected. American Defence Secretary Dick Cheney put their rejection thus: “We are not interested in a promise or a pledge, our purpose is to get Iraq out of Kuwait. The U.S. does not want Iraq to proclaim victory on ideological or any other ground that may undermine the United Nations Security Council” (African Concord Magazine 1991:4). The decision of America to lead the war against Iraq through the instrumentality of UN Charter was unmistakable, the threat to oil supplies should Iraqi friend plan proposals happen. The USA would not like a situation where military adventure such as that of Iraq would redesign the Middle East and paralyze the global economy. Times International Magazine (1990: 35 -36) noted: the last UN Resolution 678 was passed on November, 29 1990, the USA had already gotten permission for development of American troops on Saudi Arabia soil. The fallout - Italy and Soviet Union at that time decided to declare their non – involvement of their troops in the battle because enough opportunities existed at that point for negotiation which the USA and Great Britain refused to adopt.

Crimea in Ukraine was annexed since 2014, and subsequently four major Ukrainian cities were overrun in 2022 by Russian forces, yet United Nations Security Council and United States of America were helpless to apply force even when sanctions against Russia could not work. Instead, Putin sent his ally Kiril Dmitriev a senior Russian official to hold talk with Steve Witkoff a close ally of Trump to end the conflict in Ukraine (Washington Post, April 2 2025). Again, Marco Rubio U.S Secretary of States was in NATO meeting at its headquarters over the conflict in Ukraine and worked out with the following remark: “President Trump is against NATO that does not have capability that it needs to fulfill the obligations that the treaty imposes upon each and every member state” (New York Times April 11, 2025). But the UN in a space of August 2 to November 29th 1990 passed twelve resolutions over the annexation of Kuwait by Iraq. The last Resolution was UN Security Council Resolution 678 which mandated UN Secretary General Javier Perez de Culler to take inventory, custody of Kuwaiti population register which

covers up to August 1, 1990, a day before invasion. Iraq was not given reasonably space for negotiation before UN constituted forces began attacking Iraq. Italy felt non-involvement of their troops, because there are opportunities for negotiation which USA and Great Britain refused to adopt.

Theoretical Analysis

Military conflict, apart from war, encompasses armed intervention, armed incident, military coup, military blockage, and perhaps demonstration of power among other things. In line with force theory of analysis, Carl von Clausewitz (1780–1831), Prussian military General noted that; “war is distinguished by the very close relationship between politics, nation and war, the priority of politics towards war, and treating war (violence) as a political tool”. Nye, (2004: 49) explores the concepts of soft power and hard power in international relations in relation to achievement of national interest. The dynamics of Nye’s application of power is useful for understanding force theory. The theory enumerated that soft power refers to ability to achieve goals through the use of influence or attraction. While hard power relied mostly on the use of coercion and application of force as deterrence. Mearsheimer, (2019: 101) talked about the use of force in international relations where he outlined that state acquires power to limit the power of other states, which often times lead to war.

Carl Clausewitz (1832) force theory was adopted for the purposes of this study. Carl Von Clausewitz noted on his force theory that “War is the continuation of policy with other means”. In other words, every era has its wars that is why war over the last decades has gradually and intangibly changed its character. Alvin & Heidi (1980: 45) wrote about the dimension of a modern war. This couple examine the aspects of modern war. The main thesis of their publication “War and anti-war” is that there are three civilization waves, which relate directly to all three waves of war. The first one mentioned by the authors is the agrarian wave, the second is called industrial and the third-modern (post-industrial). The symbols of each are respectively: a hoe, an assembly belt and a computer, which represent those waves of wars. The wars of the so called third wave, are the wars of constantly forming post-Cold-War international order through application and use of force. In other words, Force becomes inevitable when other means of conflict resolution have failed to achieve the desired goals.

Gaps in Literature

There are myriads of roles on UN Peacekeeping force and conflicts resolution that has been carried out by UN in Liberia, Kosovo, Cyprus and numerous other countries. However, Gulf Crisis 1990-1991 and Ukraine Russia conflicts explores how the UN's approach to peace-keeping has changed over time. The Ukraine- Russia conflicts has raised debates about UN inability to muzzle its subjects through the Security Council against Russia. The study examines comparative challenges of enforcement in the context of veto power state.

Methodology

The research design for this study is descriptive through qualitative contents analysis of the roles of UN in crisis resolution especially as it concerns Gulf Crisis of 1990–1991 and Ukraine–Russia conflict (2022–2025). The study interrogated statistical differences and similarities of UN's interventions and outcomes through comparative perusal of the two conflicts. The data to this research is collected through systematic literature reviews (SLR) of secondary data regarding the UN roles in both conflicts. The data was analyzed through thematic contents of events as it occurred in the two conflicts respectively.

UN and Gulf Crisis

The UN passed twelve resolutions between August 2, 1990 Iraq invasion of Kuwait and January 15, 1991 deadline given to Iraq to withdraw her troops from Kuwait territories (Aja, 1999: 222-225).

- a. In August 2, 1990, UN Security Council (UNSC) resolution 660 was passed condemning Iraq invasion of Kuwait. The vote was 14 against 0, with Yemen abstaining, sponsored by Canada, Cote de Ivorie, Ethiopia, Finland, France, Malaysia, United Kingdom and USA.
- b. UNSC, Resolution 661 (1990) called all countries to stop importing all commodities and products from Iraq and Kuwait including exportations to both countries. Medical supplies and humanitarian export of food stuff were exempted. The resolution was passed by 13 against 0, Cuba and Yemen abstaining.
- c. In August 9, UNSC Resolution 662 was passed. The resolution declared annexation of Kuwait as 19th province of Iraq illegal. The UN advised all nations to refrain from indirect recognition of annexation.

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- d. UNSC, Resolution 664 was adopted on August 18, 1990 which demanded that Iraq should permit foreign nationals to leave Kuwait and Iraq. The resolution was passed when Saddam Hussein declared that citizens of other countries are not permitted to leave. The resolution was unanimous vote, reaffirms UNSC Resolution 662.
 - e. UNSC, Resolution 665 was issued on August 25, 1990 which authorized member states cooperating with government of Kuwait to use measures commensurate with specific circumstances to ensure that sanctions against Iraq was implemented. The resolution was adopted by 13 against 0, Cuba and Yemen abstaining. Co-sponsored by Canada, Cote de Ivorie, Finland, United Kingdom, USA and Zaire.
 - f. UNSC, Resolution 666, 667, and 669 were passed on September, 13, 16 and 24 respectively in 1990. Resolution 666 was voted to establish procedure for determining the humanitarian needs for food supplies to civilian populations in Kuwait and Iraq due to suffering from trade embargo. Resolution 667 was adopted condemning Iraq violation of diplomatic premises in Kuwait and abduction of diplomatic personnel and other foreign nationals. While resolution 669 was adopted for UN to examine request for assistance and aid to Kuwait under Article 50 of the UN Charter and to make recommendations concerning action.
 - g. UNSC, Resolution 670 was adopted on September 25, 1990 to impose air transport embargo against Iraq. The resolution required that each member state to take necessary action to ensure aircraft registered in its territory comply with the UN economic sanction against Iraq.
 - h. UNSC, Resolution 674 was adopted on October 22, 1990 calling all states to collect evidences of Iraq human right abuses in Kuwait and financial losses caused by invasion. The resolution reminded Iraq that under international law, it is responsible for any loss, damage or injury of Kuwaiti's and foreign nationals as a result of occupation of Kuwait.
 - i. UNSC, Resolution 676 was passed on November 28, 1990 which condemned Iraq attempt to alter the demographic composition of the population of Kuwait, history and civil records as maintained by legitimate government of Kuwait. The resolution mandated the then UN General Secretary Javier Perez de Culler to take inventory of Kuwait population register which covers up to August 1, 1990, a day before invasion.

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- j. UNSC, Resolution 678 was the final resolution against Iraq invasion. It was adopted on November 29, 1990 with 12 votes against 2 with China abstaining. The resolution stated that unless Iraq fully complies by January 15th January 1991 deadline unconditionally, the UN members might use all necessary means to restore international peace and security in the Gulf state.

Aja (1999) maintained that on January 16, 1991 the UN began operations against Iraq. First, Iraq responded by firing some shots of Scud- missiles against Israel as a counter measure to escalate the crisis; but US cautioned Israel to use anti – nuclear mask instead of revenge. The UN left enforcement of the resolutions to countries that contributed troops. So, USA which has largest troops to the coalition of forces took the lead and timings, even decided when Iraq was weak enough for cease-fire. Iraq only fired some harmless far-sighted shots against the Allied Forces. On 27th February 1991, Iraq surrendered and the US – led coalition forces suspended the military action against Iraq (Iwobi, 1991).

UN's Response to Ukraine–Russia Conflicts, and the Challenges

- a. In 2022, the General Assembly adopted a resolution condemning Russia attempted annexation of four Ukraine cities – Donetsk, Kherson, Luhansk and Zaporizhzhia. The resolution was sustained by 143 votes, 5 against and 35 absented.
- b. The UN set up high level human rights monitoring group to collate evidences of human rights violations and abuses in Ukraine for accountability, and
- c. The General Assembly of UN approved Commission to investigate war crime in Ukraine with documented evidences of Russian war crimes, torture, rape and deportation of children to Russia.

Challenges

UN responses to investigate Russia action and to take decisive action was limited by Russian veto power in UN Security Council. Daniel (2025) Wall Street Journal (WSJ), reported that NATO troops carried out drills in February 2025 from Ukraine border to test a quick reaction force over increasing dimensions of Russian attacks. The NATO's military muscle was unusual because European nations carried out the exercise without USA. But US President, Donald Trump said a lot of work had to be done ahead of

his planned talk with Russian leader in terms of ending the conflict in Ukraine. The conflict has decimated Ukrainian environment, causing great floods, wildfires and pollutions. The New York Times (4th April 2025), reported execution of prisoners of war near Novoivanovka in Kursk regions of Russia. New York Times also reported on (5th April 2025), that Zelensky home town Kryvyi Rih was attacked, 16 people were killed by Russian drones. The Magazine noted that the attack targeted Western military instructors in Ukraine. Nineteen were killed on 7th April 2025 in central Kyiv while at Sumy northeastern Ukraine thirty – two people were killed on 12th April 2025, New York Times 13th April 2025 reported.

This research discovered that liberalism policies of Mikhail Gorbachev has completely vanished from Russian policy. Vladimir Putin is determined to superintend its former empires. Georgi & Lytvynenko (2025) WSJ reported that Russian Foreign Minister Sergei Lavrov demanded international recognition of Russian control over Crimea and four other Ukrainian regions. The Russian president, Vladimir Putin had in 2024 rejected an immediate cease – fire with Ukraine, accusing USA as acting on the interest of Ukraine. Example, New York Times (30th March, 2025) reported untold stories of American hidden roles in Ukraine against Russian invading armies. According to the report, the secret partnership was based out of U.S military garrison command in Wiesbaden, Germany. The Magazine noted that the command is guiding big picture battle strategy and precision targeting information down to soldiers in the field.

Key Differences and Similarities on UN's Roles

Differences:

- a. The UN's response to Gulf Crisis was marked by quick resolutions. There was deadline to unconditionally withdrawal of troops from Kuwait and eventual deployment of Allied forces. However, UN's response to Russia-Ukraine conflict has been on negotiations and appeals.
- b. The two conflicts took place in difference geopolitical setting and era. For example, Gulf Crisis took place immediately after Cold War, while Russia-Ukraine conflicts are happening in multi-polar era.
- c. Russia as a belligerent state is a permanent member of the UN Security Council and she has a power of veto, while Iraq as aggressor had no veto power and she was not a member of the Security Council.

Similarities:

- a. The Gulf Crisis and Russian – Ukraine conflicts both had evidences of annexations. Therefore, Iraq and Russia are all belligerent state which was an act against UN Charter.
- b. Both Iraq and Russia rejected UN's resolutions to pull out from the occupied territories of another sovereign states.

Discussion of Findings

The UN is stuck in dealing with veto power states, therefore its effectiveness in combating future conflicts involving multi-polar and veto power States is bleak. In other words, the inability of UN to muzzle its power against Russian annexation of some parts of Ukraine has become a subject of debate in the ability of UN combating global peace in international relations. The research observed that States without power is at the mercy of superpower states in the world. Iraq was a victim of recalcitrant state without power. Indeed, the research illuminated some lessons to states that are indifference to power possession.

The study also highlighted lessons learned from the Gulf Crisis that may be applied in line with Carl Von Clausewitz theory to the Russia – Ukraine conflicts in order to eliminate threat to world peace and making UN effective as a global peace organization. Lastly, the research threw lights on major differences and perhaps some areas of similarities in both conflicts that might be useful to UN in combating global peace and security.

Conclusion

The UN was built on normative order to exercise influence in conflict resolutions, and to prevent excess of states globally. In the Gulf Crisis, the UN achieved that through coalition of forces, regrettably Russia- Ukraine conflict have dampened the trust on UN conflict resolution approach. Russia's possession of veto has made the UN toothless and subject of debate on its effectiveness to realize world peace.

Recommendations

1. UN should explore peaceful engagement with sub –regional and continental organizations of affected State before deployment of coalition forces.

2. UN should re-structure the Permanent Security Council to reflect democratic setting among all continents; Africa had none, Europe three, Asia one and America one is statistically undemocratic; and use of veto should be $\frac{2}{3}$.
3. UN should endeavour to conduct plebiscite after annexation to the State affected to determine the validity of claims over territory before intervention can take place.
4. UN should mandate US to pull down its buffer zone in Ukraine to guarantee Russian trust on peace – building in the region.

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